

ROLE OF DISTANCE LEARNING IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract: In this article, the problem of distance learning of a foreign language is highlighted. The main attention is paid to the role of information and communication technologies in modern methods of teaching a foreign language. The definition of the concept of "distance learning" is given and its main characteristics are highlighted. Based on the comparison of the advantages and disadvantages of this type of training, an assessment of the appropriateness of its use is given. The role of teacher in this process is determined.

Key words: distance learning; information and communication technologies; ICT competence; tutor.

At this stage in the development of scientific knowledge, one of the key issues in the methodology of teaching a foreign language is the use of information and communication technologies in the learning process. A large number of scientific works of domestic scientists are devoted to the study of this issue [1-6]. Distance learning is considered to be one of the main modern teaching methods using ICT. Accordingly, one should understand what the concept of "distance learning" means. Distance learning (also used as DL) is the interaction of a teacher and students I wait at a distance, reflecting all the components inherent in the educational process (goals, content, methods, organizational forms, teaching aids) and implemented by specific means of Internet technologies or other means providing interactivity [1]. Key features of educational institutions identified by A.A. Andreev, include:

- flexibility - the schedule of classes, their duration and features are completely determined by the students themselves, who devote the subject as much time as they need to master the material;
- modularity - the ability to form a curriculum in accordance with the individual or group needs of students;
- parallelism - DL can be combined with the process of basic educational activity;
- long-range action - significant territorial remoteness of students is not a problem;
- asynchrony - the teacher and the student can work according to a convenient schedule for each, and the feedback is not necessarily adjusted in real time;
- coverage - the number of students is practically unlimited;
- profitability - proven economic efficiency of subsidiaries;
- emphasis on the teacher - the role of the teacher has changed significantly;
- emphasis on the student - students are presented with slightly different requirements than in the standard learning scheme;
- use of ICTs - ICTs are not just an auxiliary, but the main tool of DO;
- sociality - to some extent, social tension is removed, since all students receive the same opportunities;

internationality - the ability to import and export educational services [6].

All of the above can be attributed to the significant advantages of using DOs. However, in order to understand the feasibility of using DL along with the traditional form of education, one should consider its main features in more detail. Flexibility actually makes the overall learning process much easier. The principle of "selection" is applied here, when the student chooses only the necessary disciplines and devotes most of the study time to them. This training system has long established itself in the United States. Thus, one can judge about the real applied value of its use. Parallelism is today a fundamental factor of DO. In the modern world, this is the most valuable "commodity". Time limit always entails inconvenience and inability to carry out one or another activity. Accordingly, DL allows us to synchronize the

main learning process (university education) with the distance learning process. As a result, information is received through two parallel channels at once, neither of which interferes with the other. Long-range action can also be called the main criterion for the ease of use of DOs. The lack of qualified personnel has become the number one problem. Distance learning allows you to overcome this barrier, because one qualified teacher is able to conduct classes with a large number of students from different cities and even countries. Distance in this case does not matter. At the same time, the number of students is practically unlimited due to the peculiarities of DL as a type of educational process. When listing the advantages of distance learning, special attention is required to determine the role of the teacher in this process. So, usually we use the term teacher or teacher, that is, a person who teaches us something. In English there is such an equivalent as the word teacher. It is understood that this person is endowed with a certain authority and even power. Thus, the status of the teacher is authoritarian. This is not to say that this is good or bad. To some extent, this approach allows you to maintain discipline in the classroom, avoid familiarity on the part of students and maintain interest in the teacher as a key figure in regulating the educational process. Speaking about the role of the teacher in the process of distance learning, it is worth giving preference to his mentoring functions, rather than regulatory ones. The role of the "overseer" is minimized. The teacher no longer has to keep a close eye on student behavior and attention and focus. He focuses his attention directly on providing material in the most accessible form and on solving specific educational problems. It would be logical to endow the teacher with mentoring functions, then there will be an opportunity, without losing credibility, serve as an example for students and act as an advisor. In this case, the more appropriate English term would be the word tutor, hence the essential difference between teacher and mentor. That is why the term tutor can often be found in scientific literature.

With additional education, a tutor can use the following forms of knowledge control:

- 1) actually controlling, or checking;
- 2) estimated;
- 3) educational;
- 4) managing (correcting);
- 5) diagnosing;
- 6) warning;
- 7) stimulating or motivating;
- 8) generalizing;
- 9) developing, educating and disciplining [7].

In distance learning, the teacher's ICT competence and writing skills come to the fore. The importance of his organizational skills remains high. Under the ICT competence of the teacher M.N. Evstigneev proposes to understand “a construct consisting of theoretical knowledge about modern information and communication technologies and practical skills in creating and using educational Internet resources, social services Web 2.0 and other ICT technologies in the process of formation of language skills and the development of speech skills in teaching a foreign language and the culture of the country of the target language ”[8]. Thus, the ICT competence of a teacher is not only factual knowledge about the functioning and capabilities of information and communication technologies in the learning process, but also the ability to apply this knowledge in the process of teaching a foreign language.

Also, do not overshadow the personal qualities of mentors, which can be of significant benefit. The creative aspect of a tutor's activity can manifest itself not only in the context of the lesson, but also in the preparation of curricula and even websites. If the teacher has the necessary level of knowledge and preparedness, he himself can develop resources, necessary for him in the learning process. The ideal scheme is when the student himself gets acquainted with the new material through cognition, turning to the teacher for help in case of problems. In this case, the Internet

is positioned as an auxiliary mechanism that combines both the information itself and the means of its processing.

The teacher should do the following:

- to form motivation among students;
- set specific goals and objectives for students;
- transfer your knowledge and experience;
- organize activities;
- to establish interaction between listeners;
- monitor the learning process;
- control the quality of knowledge and professional skills.

In DL, the ICT competence of the student is no less important, without it it will become impossible to build such an atypical learning process. According to A.A. Andreev, distance learning tools are: - books (in paper and electronic form);

- online learning materials;
- computer training systems in conventional and multimedia versions;
- educational and informational audio and video materials;
- laboratory remote workshops;
- simulators;
- databases and knowledge with remote access;
- electronic libraries with remote access;
- didactic materials based on expert training systems;
- didactic materials based on geographic information systems [6]

As a result, comparing all the advantages and a few disadvantages of DL, we can judge the sufficient effectiveness of this type of training. Its main advantages are long-range action, flexible training schedule, and asynchrony. In addition, it is important that DOs can produce it is in parallel with other types of educational activities, and the audience coverage here is practically unlimited.

Despite the change in the role of the teacher in comparison with the classical teaching model, one cannot speak of any cardinal changes. The trainer will also continue to share their experience and knowledge in the learning process. The change will consist only in the fact that he will retrain from “overseer” to “mentor”.

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